

JOHN FOWLES'S VARIATIONS IN *THE COLLECTOR*

Perry Nodelman

The co-editor of a recent issue of *Modern Fiction Studies* devoted to John Fowles says it contains no article on *The Collector* because Fowles's first novel has been "so oft-analyzed" that critics "seem hard-pressed to say anything new about it."¹ What has stifled debate is the idea that being "collected" and held captive changes Fowles's protagonist, the young art student Miranda, for the better; most commentators agree with Miranda's conviction that "the person I was and would have stayed if this hadn't happened was not the person I now want to be."² In the preface to *The Aristos*, Fowles himself seems to support this interpretation; he says that Miranda

had well-to-do parents, good educational opportunity, inherited aptitude and intelligence. That does not mean that she was perfect. Far from it—she was

¹William J. Palmer, "John Fowles and the Crickets," *Modern Fiction Studies* 31.1 (1985): 11. I would like to offer my thanks to Frederick M. Holmes for his help in my education in Fowles.

²John Fowles, *The Collector* (1963; rpt. London: Triad/Panther, 1976) 261. All further references to *The Collector* are to this edition. Arnold Davidson speaks of Miranda's "growing awareness" ("Caliban and the Captive Maiden: John Fowles' *The Collector* and Irving Wallace's *The Fan Club*," *Studies in the Humanities* 8.2 [1981]: 29), Patricia Beatty of her "rebirth" ("John Fowles' Clegg: Captive Landlord of Eden," *Ariel* 13.3 [1982]: 75), Robert Huffaker of her "maturing attitude" and "amplified self-recognition" (*John Fowles* [Boston: Twayne, 1980] 88, 89), Shyamal Bagchee of her "incredibly fast spiritual growth in captivity" ("*The Collector*: The Paradoxical Imagination of John Fowles," *Journal of Modern Literature* 8.2 [1980-81]: 234). Peter Conradi says "it is Miranda's imprisonment that begins to emancipate her" (*John Fowles* [London and New York: Methuen, 1982] 23), Dwight Eddins that "she has progressed significantly from her starting point" ("John Fowles: Existence as Authorship," *Contemporary Literature* 17 [1976]: 210), Heide Ziegler and Christopher Bigsby

arrogant in her ideas, a prig, a liberal-humanist snob, like so many university students. Yet if she had not died she might have become something better, the kind of being humanity so desperately needs.³

In fact, Fowles says not that Miranda has changed yet, but only that she has the *potential* for change. Despite the understandable desire of readers to sympathize with Miranda as the victim of a deranged villain, she remains throughout what Walter Allen once described her to be: “a stereotype of a stereotype, of the contemporary middle class girl of some education as we meet her on Sunday morning in the *Observer*.”⁴

In agreeing with Miranda’s claim to growth, commentators ignore the peculiar structure of the novel, which demands a more ironic, and much more interesting, reading. While commentators downplay it, the strange shape of *The Collector* is a surprise for first-time readers. In the first part of the novel, the kidnapper, Clegg, tells his own story; since that occupies almost half the novel, there is no reason to assume he won’t continue to do so. But part one ends, and instead of the expected continuation of Clegg’s story, readers suddenly find themselves reading again about the events that Clegg has already described, but now as seen by Miranda. It is this surprising switch of narrative perspective *in medias res* that forms readers’ attitudes to both Clegg and Miranda.

If Fowles had presented just Clegg’s narrative, he would have written the entertaining thriller that early reviews of the novel describe. Part one achieves exactly what readers expect of a thriller; it tells of horrifying events in terms that make them exciting but not threatening. Since the story is told in Clegg’s own words, it places us inside a repulsively alien mind, a claustrophobic prison like the one Clegg himself puts Miranda in; but Clegg is so thoroughly repulsive that any sane reader must remain separate from his perceptions of reality and thus experience the prison without feeling imprisoned by it.

As a result, the Miranda of part one is merely an idea: the archetypal maiden in distress, a role that must be filled so that the thriller

that “there are signs of a crucial recovery” (*The Radical Imagination and the Liberal Tradition: Interviews with English and American Novelists* [London: Junction, 1982] 112), and Kerry McSweeney that “the cardinal point about Miranda is that she changes greatly during the course of the novel” (“John Fowles’s Variations,” *Four Contemporary Novelists* [Kingston and Montreal: McGill-Queen’s UP, 1983] 134).

³John Fowles, *The Aristos*, rev. ed. (1968; rpt. New York: New American Library, 1975) 10. All further references to *The Aristos* are to this edition.

⁴Walter Allen, “The Achievement of John Fowles,” *Encounter* 35.2 (1970): 64.

can play itself out. Although we do, in theory, sympathize with Miranda, there is no character inside the role; nor can there be one, for the “maiden in distress” is merely a pawn in an interesting game. Should we begin to think of her as a real person, should we begin to see the human implications of this horrific situation, then the thriller would no longer be merely entertaining. We do, of course, suspect that Miranda is not what the insensitive Clegg imagines; but we cannot see what that something else might be.

It is the revelation that we must take Miranda seriously that makes the beginning of part two such a shock—a shock Fowles clearly intended, for once there is a real person inside the role, we must feel compassion for her; no matter what character Miranda reveals, as soon as she reveals any character at all she becomes human, and the book moves beyond the fake horror of the thriller. Not only can we no longer read it as a clever game designed to provide us with pretend thrills, but we must also realize the symbolic implications of what we read in part one. If Miranda is more than we thought she was, then she is certainly different from what Clegg thought she was. Freed from the prison of Clegg’s perceptions, we must now understand that Clegg has captured only his image of Miranda; as Robert Campbell says, “He won’t, refuses, to see her as a conscious subject who is constituted *as* a subject of her world; instead she is, for him, only an object in his.”⁵

The natural response to that realization is to admire Miranda for being more than the hateful Clegg can see, and dislike him even more than we did already for seeing less than there is. Since we know for sure that Clegg doesn’t see accurately, and since the inaccuracy of Clegg’s perception causes Miranda so much pain, we are likely to sympathize with Miranda and to trust her reading of events; that may be why so many readers accept the version of herself that Miranda presents.

But if Fowles had wanted us to do that, he could have more easily created trust in Miranda by alternating the two narrations throughout the book. Instead of an immersion in Clegg’s attitudes and then an immersion in Miranda’s, we would have been forced by our immediate consciousness of their differences from each other into an objective analysis of both at the same time, and that process of analysis would have encouraged us to accept as truer Miranda’s more sensitive and intelligent reading of events. Because the structure would have

⁵Robert Campbell, “Moral Sense and the Collector: The Novels of John Fowles,” *Critical Quarterly* 25.1 (1983): 45–53.

forced us as readers to become more thoughtful ourselves, we would tend to sympathize more with Miranda's thoughtfulness than with Clegg's unconsidering acceptance of received values. Furthermore, the growth that commentators perceive in Miranda would have been counterpointed by the absolute stasis of Clegg—his inability to respond to new ideas—so that the novel would have clearly made the distinction between the male as “stasis, or conservatism” and the female as “kinesis, or progress” that Fowles posits in *The Aristos* (165–66). Indeed, most commentaries on *The Collector* seem to imply that Fowles did set the book up in that way—that it consists of alternating commentaries that counterpoint Clegg's and Miranda's attitudes and perceptions.

But it doesn't. Fowles gives us first one narration almost complete, and then the other complete, and then the end of the first one. Indeed, Barry Olshen reports that in the manuscript Fowles first submitted to his publisher, these two last sequences were originally part of the first section, so that readers would have knowledge of Miranda's death before they began her diary;⁶ Fowles agreed to a change that provides some suspense, but preserved the separation of the two narratives from each other.

The main effect of that separation is to force readers to concentrate on the claustrophobia of Miranda's character—her involvement in herself—just as we had previously focused on Clegg's claustrophobia—his involvement with himself. Given the credit Miranda has built up as the maiden in distress in part one, it takes surprisingly little time for her to reveal her limitations. In the first few pages of her diary, she spouts clichés (“I love life so passionately, I never knew how much I wanted to live before” [127]), reveals a fetish for cleanliness and a reticence about bodily functions (“Hateful primitive washstand and place” [128]), prays to a God she's not sure she believes in (129), and reveals a snobbish disdain for just about everything she thinks about. This is not so much despicable as ordinary—Miranda quickly descends from being the blameless victim into a mere flawed human being.

It is these human flaws that make her more than a stock figure and allow us to sympathize with her; but, paradoxically, they also prevent us from trusting her—at least when the revelation of her flaws occurs all at once after Clegg's narrative rather than interspersed with it. Because we must focus so intensely and so exclusively on Miranda's description of her own flawed reactions, we must feel claustrophobia;

⁶Barry N. Olshen, *John Fowles* (New York: Ungar, 1978) 20.

Miranda's narration is as self-involved as is Clegg's. In part one, Clegg thinks only of his obsession with Miranda; one of the surprises of part two is how rarely Miranda thinks of it, for as Clegg rightly says at the end, her diary "shows she never loved me, she only thought of herself and the other man all the time" (286). Since it is about the "other man," the painter G. P., more than it is about Clegg, Miranda's narration is a completely different story, and therefore, we must suspect, a no more trustworthy one.

Fowles confirms those suspicions by making Miranda as obtuse about Clegg as he is obtuse about her. When she tries to seduce him, for instance, she believes his story that he is impotent and has been to a psychiatrist; but we already know from Clegg's narration that what she so readily accepts as truth is not the truth, that he made up the psychiatrist and that his real problem was the exact opposite of impotence. He does develop an erection: "What happened then was most embarrassing, I began to feel very worked up and I always understood (from something I heard in the army) that a gentleman always controls himself to the right moment and so I just didn't know what to do. . . . I got up, I was ashamed, I had to go to the window and pretend to do something to the curtain" (107-8). Ironically, it seems to be, at least in part, his disgust with his uncontrollable lust here that leads to his impotence in the scene that follows; but Miranda misinterprets his behavior by accepting his explanation, recognizing his fear, and not even considering the possibility that he might feel self-disgust: "He wanted to run away, but he couldn't" (252). Just as Clegg misunderstands Miranda, Miranda misunderstands Clegg. There is much irony when Miranda hears an airplane and records in her diary the thought, "If only people knew what they flew over. We're all in aeroplanes" (135). She too flies, over Clegg.

Fowles's work often deals with the lack of real knowledge that people have of each other. In *The Magus*, in *The French Lieutenant's Woman*, in the stories "Poor Koko" and "The Enigma" in *The Ebony Tower*, Fowles allows neither readers nor other characters to know the motives of central characters—much as Miranda and Clegg do not know each other's motives. *The Collector* is different from these stories only because its two narratives mutually provide the solutions to each other's mysteries, solutions that merely deepen the mystery.

Fowles's only other work that presents the viewpoints of more than one consciousness is the final story in *The Ebony Tower*, "The Cloud"—which is also, interestingly, the only other work by Fowles that takes us inside a woman's perceptions; it too shows how they

directly contradict a man's view of the same events. In fact, "The Cloud" emphasizes isolation: "everything became little islands, without communication."⁷ This refers to the isolation of moments in time from each other, not the isolation of people from each other; but it evokes "To Marguerite," the poem by Matthew Arnold that Fowles quotes in full in, and then refers to again at the end of, *The French Lieutenant's Woman*; throughout his work, Fowles insists again and again that "in the sea of life enisl'd . . . We mortal millions live *alone*."

Significantly, Fowles says,

I have always thought of my own novels as islands, or as islanded. I remember being forcibly struck, on my first visit to the Scillies, by the structural and emotional correspondences between visiting the different islands and any fictional text: the alternation of duller passages, "continuity" in the jargon of the cinema, and the separate island quality of other key events and confrontations — an insight, the notion of islands in the sea of story, that I could not forsake now even if I tried.⁸

This is the effect of "The Cloud," in which the isolation of the different narrative perspectives from each other shows how "everything became little islands." *The Collector* similarly consists of islands without any "sea of story" between; the "continuity" that binds the two isolated narrations together is only the extent to which they are variations on each other — the fact that they both tell of the same events but show us different aspects of them.

This sort of variation is the most characteristic gesture of Fowles's work: the juxtaposition of characters and situations and ideas that are alike, but different enough to comment on each other. In "A Personal Note" in *The Ebony Tower*, Fowles says that the working title of the book was "Variations," and that each story is a variation on earlier work.⁹ *Mantissa* consists of a series of similar encounters — the same basic story involving somewhat different characters. The two versions of *The Magus* Fowles has published effectively operate as variations on each other for readers of both. The two (or maybe three) different endings to *The French Lieutenant's Woman* are variations of each other, and they throw interesting light on the beginning of part four of *The Collector*; its first sentence — "As it happened, things

⁷John Fowles, "The Cloud," *The Ebony Tower* (1974; rpt. New York: New American Library, 1974) 244.

⁸John Fowles, *Islands* (London: Cape, 1978) 30.

⁹*The Ebony Tower* 109.

turned out rather different” (286)—makes it a variation on Clegg’s plans for a romantic death of his own, which precede it in part three.

Presented in its completeness following Clegg’s complete narrative, Miranda’s story becomes a variation like these others. Not only does it present a different version of the same events, it is also a variation of them; Miranda’s obsession with G. P. strangely parallels Clegg’s obsession with her. By offering these counterpointed relationships, Fowles forces us to consider their similarities and differences, and leads us to a startling conclusion: not only is Miranda’s diary a variation of Clegg’s narrative, but Miranda is herself a variation on Clegg—a version of the same character.

According to Kerry McSweeney, “For all the differences in their attitudes to sex and love, both Clegg and Miranda are virgins and both are in their different ways untested by interpersonal experience”;¹⁰ indeed, the apparent difference in their attitudes hides a surprising amount of similarity. They are both obsessed by ideas of beauty. They both think themselves superior to others, to other members of their class and especially to their family members, because their taste is more refined; and they both use their conviction of superiority to justify callousness. They both hate dirt and are uncomfortable about bodily functions. They both think sex is disgusting, and justify their disgust with the philosophical conviction that bodily lust is corrupting. Clegg claims that ordinary lust is “some crude animal thing I was born without” (10); Miranda says, “Sex doesn’t matter. Love does” (249). They both greatly admire a person of the opposite sex whom they feel disdain for but pretend to believe to be better than themselves, and they both see this admiration as a sign of their own refinement. They both confuse their admiration with love, and are horrified when the people they admire reveal a merely human carnality. Miranda is as offended by G. P.’s interest in sex—“his one horrid weakness” (151)—as Clegg is offended by her sexuality: “She was like all women, she had a one-track mind” (113). Clegg is more right than he knows when he says, “She hated dirt as much as I do. . . . She told me once it was a sign of madness to want everything clean. If that is so, then we must both have been mad” (69).

Fowles calls attention to the similarities between Clegg and Miranda by making both of them collectors. Clegg collects butterflies; Miranda speaks of “all the horrid people who wouldn’t give me money when I was collecting” (221). Both collect in the service of their aspira-

¹⁰McSweeney 131.

tions for something better than ugly, normal reality—he for beauty, she to make the world a better place. Miranda may also be the symbolic sort of collector that Clegg is; although she claims, “I couldn’t ever be a Toinette. A collector of men” (257), she often speaks of men as objects she has collected: “I began to feel he was mine, that I knew all about him. And I hated it when he went off to Italy like that, without telling me. Not because I was seriously in love with him, but because he was vaguely mine and didn’t get permission from me” (147).

There are, of course, important differences between Clegg and Miranda; if nothing else, they express the same basic characteristics in terms of significant differences between typical male and female behavior, and between typical lower class and middle class behavior. Nevertheless, the parallels between Clegg and Miranda are the most intriguing feature of the novel: why did Fowles make the victim so much like the victimizer?

Fowles provides an explanation in his comment on Clegg in *The Aristos*: “I tried to show that his evil was largely, perhaps wholly, the result of a bad education, a mean environment, being orphaned: all factors over which he had no control. In short, I tried to establish the virtual *innocence* of the Many. Miranda, the girl he imprisoned, had very little more control than Clegg over what she was” (10). Here Fowles suggests that neither Clegg nor Miranda is anything much more than or different from the social forces surrounding them; in fact, they are virgins in every sense, with no real experience, no character, no meaning beyond the values they’ve collected unconsciously from the world around them. Fowles has created two complex, subtly drawn characters the essence of whose being is an utter lack of individual character. As a result, Miranda and Clegg sum up the conventional values and attitudes of their sexes and their classes, and their story reveals how those values imprison them.

Miranda’s story is most essentially a variation of Clegg’s because, even though their differences of class and gender cause them to express them differently, they do share a basic set of values. Both share conceptions of the differences between classes. For Clegg, Miranda’s “educated” voice and her being “refined” (6) mark her superiority; he says, “She often went on about how she hated class distinction, but she never took me in. It’s the way people speak that gives them away, not what they say. You only had to see her dainty ways to see how she was brought up. . . . Stop thinking about class, she’d say. Like a rich man telling a poor man to stop thinking about money” (42). Miranda shares Clegg’s perception of her superiority to him and also blames it on class:

she sees him as “a victim of a miserable nonconformist suburban world and a miserable social class, the horrid timid copycatting genteel in-between class” (172), and she attaches the same significance to speech as he does, saying that “He’s got one of those funny inbetween voices, uneducated trying to be educated” (131).

The confusion Clegg and Miranda both feel about their relationship to each other is based on their shared attitudes toward class differences. He believes he is better than his class and therefore good enough to deserve her, his social superior. But he dislikes it both when she acts superior and rejects him, and when she brings herself down to what he considers to be the low level of women of his own class and tries to seduce him. Meanwhile, she too sees herself as freed from the deficiencies of her class, and she wants to educate him, to make him a good socialist like herself; yet she despises him exactly to the extent that he’s educated himself beyond his class and into an imitation of the mannerisms of her class. She dislikes it both when he makes it clear he thinks of her as his superior and when he dares to imagine that he’s good enough for her.

The ironies here all have to do with their shared conviction that she is superior to him; he is the brute animal, she the pure, and purifying, spirit. Significantly, the conventional relationship between men and women in traditional versions of romantic love is exactly that. According to the ideals of courtly love that still underlie popular conceptions of romance, a man loves a woman because she is better than, i.e., purer than, he—worthy of worship because she is beyond mere animal passion, so that his desire for her lifts him too above the animal. She cannot be passionate, of course, for that would prove she wasn’t enough above mere brute animality to be a worthy object of desire; as Miranda herself says, “it’s this weird male thing. . . . They sulk if you don’t give, and hate you when you do” (254). To fulfill his desire with a worthy object, then, a man has no choice but to take a woman against her will—just as Clegg “collects” Miranda.

For both Clegg and Miranda herself, Miranda is exactly the desirable woman proclaimed by these conventions. He uses the language of the tradition when he says, “I knew my love was worthy of her” (30). Indeed, as Janet Lewis and Barry Olshen suggest, Clegg is an exaggerated version, “an ironic foil to the romantic lover”;¹¹ and Miranda is the typical object of courtly love, pursued because she is

¹¹Janet E. Lewis and Barry N. Olshen, “John Fowles and the Medieval Romance Tradition,” *Modern Fiction Studies* 31.1 (1985): 15–30.

pure—and, indeed, exactly as untouched, as virginal, and as repelled by lust as Clegg imagines her to be, for ironically, of course, he is not mistaken in his reading of her character. He admires her because she is purer than he; and when she gives him what she believes he wants, he no longer finds her desirable—in fact, her attempted seduction implies two truths he would prefer not to acknowledge: one, he is himself a mere brute like everyone else, the animal he thought he was transcending in his love for her; and two, so is she.

In a note to *The Aristos*, Fowles says that the central principle of “amour courtois” is “the idea that truly noble love is never consummated. It was, so to speak, a game without a prize—and whose only purpose could therefore be the continuance of the game” (221). The version of that game described in *The Collector* ends with the threat of consummation. Miranda’s conventional assumptions about love and art led her to offer her idealized Paston love without sex when the real Paston wanted sex without love; now her conventional assumptions about sex and class lead her to offer Clegg sex without love when what he wants, clearly, is love without sex—a return of the worship he feels for her that would lift them both onto a higher spiritual plane. Thinking about what she knows of men, she convinces herself that Clegg “has some secret. He must want me physically” (248). But Clegg’s actual secret is the exact opposite: “It was almost like she was stupid, plain stupid. Of course she wasn’t really, it was just that she didn’t see how to love me in the right way” (113). As his pornographic pursuits show, “the right way” is to remain at a distance from him, and to allow him to believe she adores him as passively as he can imagine a photographic image does.

In other words, what Clegg wants from Miranda is what Miranda wants from Paston: spiritual love. Her story parallels his. Furthermore, that Miranda is literally swept off her feet and taken away by Clegg is both an expression of the romantic ideals he aspires to and, ironically, a mirror of her own confused ideas about sexuality. Within the tradition Clegg represents, normal sexuality is always an act of rape, the strong male forcing his will on the weak woman, for as Fowles says in *The Aristos*, “To the Adam in man, woman is no more than a rapable receptacle”; he also speaks of “this male association of femininity with rapability” (166). Miranda shares these conventional ideas; her romantic fantasies always involve her being forced against her will. When G. P. talks to her, she thinks “he’s drawing a net around me” (186). And when she imagines love, it is a question of being overpowered: “I know I have love pent up in me, I shall throw myself away,

lose my heart and my body and my mind and soul to some cad like G. P. Who'll betray me" (245). Miranda even has surprisingly similar rape fantasies involving both Clegg and G. P., both the man she hates and the man she claims to love. Near the beginning of her diary, she reports telling Clegg "that if he suddenly wanted to rape me, I wouldn't resist, I would let him do what he liked, but that I would never speak to him again" (147); near the end, she writes, "I think — I will give myself to G. P. He can have me. And whatever he does to me I shall still have my woman-me he can never touch" (258). For Miranda, sex and even love are always like rape — and so Clegg's collecting her is something like love, for her as well as for him.

Clegg shows how much he sees his pursuit of Miranda as an expression of conventional ideas of romance when he says, "She smelt so nice I could have stood like that all the evening. It was like being in one of those adverts come to life" (89). Miranda reveals a similarly conventional view of romance in a fantasy that does not involve Clegg but sounds suspiciously like her situation with him, as she speaks of two people alone in "White cottages. . . . We are together, very close in spirit. All silly magazine stuff, really" (245). Seen in these terms, what Clegg does to Miranda is not so much a perversion of conventional male attitudes to sexuality as an exaggeration of them that points out their perverse implications; and how she responds is not so much a perversion as an exaggeration of conventional female responses.

Miranda spoils the "silly magazine stuff" for Clegg when she tries to seduce him; but the ending of the story continues to follow the conventional patterns. Having become for Clegg a symbol of the corruption of an ideal, Miranda is now evil; he must dispose of her, and replace her with a new ideal. Since this is an extreme version of the story, Miranda actually dies of physical contact and the end of love: she catches the cold that kills her when she kisses Clegg, and dies of it because he no longer finds her worthy of his care. Clegg's story also continues to be an exaggerated version of the conventional one: having learned cynicism from his experience with Miranda, he will no longer actually pursue an ideal to satisfy his sexual fantasies. Miranda wanted to educate Clegg into being a better person by exposing the flaws in his ideals; and she did indeed teach him that, but not as she might have hoped. For what she teaches him, in being so snobbishly herself, is that a truly superior woman will look down on him too much to satisfy him; his next victim will be a woman who looks like Miranda but who lacks her class superiority — an ideal as fake as the falsely admiring woman of pornographic photographs. She will be "someone who would respect me more. Someone ordinary I could teach" (287).

Indeed, Clegg seems to have picked up some pointers from G. P.'s behavior as Miranda records it in her diary; Miranda loved G. P. because he was better than she, someone who could and did teach her; and having learned that student-teacher relationship from G. P., she then thought of Clegg as someone she could teach herself as G. P. had taught her — someone to whom she felt superior rather than inferior. Clegg then learns to seek someone with the same relationship to himself as Miranda had with G. P. and believed Clegg had with her: someone inferior to himself, a woman he can teach. He will teach her how to please him — as, perhaps, G. P. taught Miranda, and as she unconsciously wants Clegg to learn from her. In the class-ridden world of *The Collector*, desire is always associated with the need for power.

That Clegg learns Miranda's lesson so perversely suggests the possibility that she, too, perverts and misuses the wisdom she learned from G. P. — in particular, his ideas about the Few and the Many which, we learn from *The Aristos*, Fowles also shares. She certainly does at the start, when she uses these ideas to justify self-indulgence and snobbishness. But not, commentators insist, throughout, for if Miranda unintentionally teaches Clegg to be a worse person than he was, then perhaps, as she claims, his treatment of her does teach her to be a better person than she was.

Yet despite her supposed new wisdom, Miranda still reveals a lack of self-perception. Although she claims that “the last of the Lady-mont me” is dead (254), she still sees sex as an ugly but necessary adjunct to spiritual love: “My body doesn't count any more. If he just wants that he can have it” (257). She quickly turns her supposed new freedom into her old need for power; her new self is even more ready than her old one to say “Men are a joke,” and she uses her new idea of her power over men to justify lack of contact, saying that G. P. will never really touch her no matter how close they become. She then describes two dreams: the first is yet another fantasy of love without sex, as she stands with a man in a corn field: “The *purest* spring feeling” (259). The second reiterates her earlier rape fantasies, as a black horse crashes through her window and attacks her. As her sickness advances at the end, she turns full circle, and as at the beginning, prays to a God she claims not to believe in.

So Miranda does not really grow. Given her situation, she cannot; she is right to fear rape and violence, right to see the relationships of men and women as a struggle for power. In a final irony, Clegg's brutish treatment of her illness forces her to pervert the new ideas she thinks she has espoused into her old prejudices; and meanwhile, her

attempt to act on her newfound freedom and seduce Clegg is exactly what leads him to become the brute he had resisted being before. Although both change toward the end, the changes merely deepen the conventional attitudes they have always acted upon. Doomed from the start by their shared ideas about sex and class, neither Miranda nor Clegg can grow because they can do nothing but confirm for each other what they believe to be true already.

Finally, then, Miranda's inability to act on her new ideas may imply that escape from the prison of convention is impossible. *The Collector* exemplifies what Fowles says in *The Aristos*: "It may turn out finally that indeed we do not, in some evolutionary or biological sense, possess any free will. All our 'free' choices may be finally attributable to some conditioning over which we have no control. . . . We are in a prison cell" (68).

Yet in that same passage, Fowles goes on to say, "but it [the cell] . . . can be made to become a comparatively spacious one; and inside it we can become relatively free" (68). Imprisoned both by their attitudes and by the cruel logic of the situation, neither Clegg nor Miranda possesses any relative degree of freedom; even Miranda's claims to freedom become ironic in relation to their effect on her survival. We must ask why Fowles, whose work so centrally concerns the possibilities of freedom, would choose to describe a situation that by its very nature prevents any sense of those possibilities.

Fowles had been working on *The Magus* when the idea for *The Collector* came to him; he wrote it quickly and published it before returning to *The Magus*. In fact, *The Collector* is a variation of *The Magus*, and the nature of the variations explains its focus on imprisonment.

The two novels have intricate connections with each other. Like Clegg, Nicholas Urfe of *The Magus* is a solitary, class-conscious orphan who pursues a woman because she represents his romantic ideals; like Miranda, Urfe is a middle-class snob with a veneer of existential ideas that he uses to justify self-indulgence. Indeed, the similarities between Miranda and Clegg are reinforced by the way they both mirror the worse qualities of Urfe. Above all, however, both novels allude to Shakespeare's play *The Tempest*. Conchis, the mysterious "magus" who creates delicious fantasies on his island in order to bring about a happy ending for Urfe, is clearly a version of Prospero; so is Clegg, who also brings a young person to a secluded spot under his control. Enthralled and isolated in Conchis's domain and under his power, Urfe learns the meaning of freedom; enthralled and isolated in Clegg's

domain and under his power, Miranda learns the meaning of the opposite of freedom: imprisonment.

The Prospero of *The Collector* is also its Caliban, for Miranda thinks of Clegg as Caliban—even though he falsely claims his first name is Ferdinand. This conflation of magician and savage beast in one character suggests that the main problem the novel explores is a concern Fowles has often expressed about the novelist's Prosperolike power to control the destinies of his characters, which he sees as an intrusion upon the freedom of his readers. In *Islands*, Fowles says, "The text may demand action; but something in its external, objective, 'other' nature is always inherently alienating of action in all who did not perform the original action of its creation. In simplest terms, and even at the very highest level, it is someone else's magic."¹²

This power of the novelist is the power Conchis has over Urfe—a power he uses, paradoxically, to provide both Urfe and readers of the novel with ideas about the importance of freedom. But the more Conchis's "magic" persuades Urfe to share his ideas about freedom, the less free he leaves Urfe to think differently from himself; and the more Fowles's "magic" descriptions of Conchis's effect on Urfe persuade readers to share his ideas about freedom, the more he limits their freedom to reach their own conclusions. In other words, the extent to which the "magic" is effective is the extent to which it undercuts its own presumed goals.

Concerns of this sort later caused Fowles to give readers of *The French Lieutenant's Woman* the opportunity to choose their own ending. The two isolated narratives of *The Collector* offer its readers a freedom of interpretation that *The Magus* lacks; writing it may well have been an attempt by Fowles to find a way around the freedom-denying implications of the other novel. The Prospero figure in *The Magus* is so strong, and so clearly right, that even a desperately ambiguous ending—even, since the publication of the revised version, two desperately ambiguous endings—cannot hide the fact. Consequently, the most significant aspect of the relationship between *The Magus* and *The Collector* is the way that Clegg's imprisonment of Miranda makes clear these implications of Conchis's treatment of Urfe; both Urfe and Miranda are forced to learn about freedom by suffering imprisonment, but Miranda's story reveals the oppressive cruelty downplayed in Urfe's. There are further ironic implications in the Prosperolike role the pompous G. P. plays in Miranda's life, and the strong

¹²*Islands* 101, 104.

possibility that G. P. might be using his supposed wisdom merely to seduce Miranda. That makes the relationship between G. P. and Miranda an ugly parody of Conchis's seduction of Urfe—and, since Conchis and G. P. both frequently spout ideas that Fowles himself expresses in his own nonfiction, of Fowles's own attempted seduction of his readers.

The Collector purges the darker implications of *The Magus* by pushing them to their most exaggerated extreme. Clegg's treatment of Miranda shows why it would be wrong for Urfe to have what he wants of the mysterious Lily. Meanwhile, Conchis is nowhere near so demonic as Clegg, and his domain is nowhere near so claustrophobic as Clegg's cottage; and the horror of both Miranda's and Clegg's imprisonment in their conventional values shows why it is right for Conchis to use any means at all to rid Urfe of his similar imprisonment.

As a sort of parody of *The Magus*, *The Collector* must deal in stereotypes—characters who cannot change, who are doomed as much by their literary genre as by their situation to lack of flexibility—lack of freedom. As McSweeney suggests, then, Miranda is indeed “a freshly realized embodiment of the archetypal figure of the Protestant heroine, the secular saint—pure, noble, selfless, highminded, and assured of her own virtue.”¹³ But she does not, as he claims, become that at the end; she is nothing else from the start. Furthermore, that is exactly what is wrong with her; *The Collector* shows that purity is often fear of lust, that nobility and selflessness are often just snobbishness, that assurance of one's own virtue may be the most deadly of sins—and that all these supposed virtues become the worst of vices when they are merely unexplored social assumptions. Indeed, the variations of *The Collector* brilliantly reveal how heroines—and heroes—who unthinkingly accept and then lust after the life-denying ideals implied by conventional social and sexual attitudes may be the most dangerously life-denying of all human beings.

University of Winnipeg

¹³McSweeney 134.